

Supplemental Data 2: Primers used for real-time quantitative PCR for metabolic gene expression.

Gene name	Gene symbol	Assay ID	Amplicon size (bp)	Accession number(s)
Beta actin*	<i>Actb</i>	Cat #4351319	61	NM_031144.3
Eukaryotic translation initiation factor 2A*	<i>Eif2a</i>	Rn01494813_m1	82	NM_001109339.1
Glucose-6-phosphatase, catalytic subunit	<i>G6pc</i>	Rn00689876_m1	64	NM_013098.2 NM_001270849.1
Glucokinase	<i>Gck</i>	Rn00561265_m1	58	NM_001270850.1 NM_012565.2
Glucose transporter 2 [solute carrier family 2 (facilitated glucose transporter), member 2]	<i>Glut2 (Slc2a2)</i>	Rn00563565_m1	76	NM_012879.2
Glucose transporter 4	<i>Glut4</i>	Rn00562597_m1	75	NM_012751.1
Insulin receptor	<i>Insr</i>	Rn01403321_m1	76	NM_017071.2
Phosphoenolpyruvate carboxykinase 1	<i>Pck1</i>	Rn01529014_m1	87	NM_198780.3
Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma, coactivator 1 alpha	<i>Ppargc1a</i>	Rn00580241_m1	94	NM_031347.1
Ribosomal protein L19*	<i>Rpl19</i>	Rn00821265_g1	57	NM_031103.1

* Endogenous control.

All primers were Assay-on-Demand primer/probe sets from ThermoFisher Scientific (Richlands, QLD, Australia)